

TENSILE, COMPRESSIVE AND IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF HIGH VOLUME-FRACTION RESIN TRANSFER MOULDED FLAX AND GLASS FIBRE EPOXY LAMINATES FOR SPORTING APPLICATIONS

Henry Ling¹, Mark Battley¹ and Tom Allen¹

¹Centre for Advanced Composite Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Auckland, Private Bag 92019, Auckland, New Zealand

Email: henry.ling@auckland.ac.nz, web page: <https://www.auckland.ac.nz>

Keywords: Impact, Mechanical properties, Natural fibre composites, Sporting applications, Flax fibre

ABSTRACT

Flax fibres have shown promise as a suitable 'green' alternative to glass fibres. Their specific strength and specific stiffness is similar to that of E-glass fibres. However, to date, composites manufactured with flax fibres have typically had lower specific strengths than glass-fibre composites. There is also only limited information available on the performance of high volume-fraction (>50%) flax/epoxy composites, which is the range of volume-fractions likely to be used in high performance applications.

This study compares the quasi-static tensile and compressive mechanical properties and dynamic impact performance of high volume-fraction flax/epoxy and glass-fibre laminates manufactured using Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). Panels were manufactured from woven 150gsm flax and 285gsm glass fibres with Gurit Prime 20LV Epoxy resin.

Two different comparisons were made. The first was between 4mm thick flax/epoxy and glass-fibre panels each with 20 layers and hence the same number of interfaces between lamina. These interfaces are where delamination can occur, so are important for impact performance. The second case compared two panels having the same areal weight; a 6 mm flax/epoxy panel and a 4 mm glass-fibre panel with 32 and 20 plies respectively. As flax fibres have a lower density than glass fibres, panels of the same weight are thicker which may provide an advantage for out-of-plane properties, such as impact and flexural strength.

Results from this study indicate that flax-fibre laminates, even on a specific basis, have a lower tensile, compressive and impact performance than thickness or weight equivalent glass-fibre laminates. Potential improvement may be seen by combining glass and flax fibres into a hybrid laminate to leverage the sustainability and lower density of flax fibres.

1 INTRODUCTION

Some natural fibres have been shown to have specific properties higher than that of glass fibres. Table 1 summarises the properties of commonly used fibres [1], showing that flax fibres have a very similar specific strength and stiffness to E-glass. Though natural fibres such as flax are reported to have promising specific strength and stiffness [2], natural-fibre composites have not yet been consistently produced with specific properties comparable to glass-fibre composites. This is believed to be due to the lower compatibility between the natural fibre and the matrix material, and the inhomogeneous nature of natural fibres, which introduces defects in the composite [3].

Table 1: Fibre properties [1]

Property		E-Glass	Flax	Hemp	Jute	Cotton
<i>Tensile Strength</i>	[MPa]	2600	1445	696	550	850
<i>Young's Modulus</i>	[GPa]	73	40	90	0.78	8
<i>Density</i>	[kgm ⁻³]	2580	1500	1490	1450	1540
<i>Specific Strength</i>	[MPa/(kgm ⁻³)]	1.008	0.963	0.467	0.379	0.552
<i>Specific Modulus</i>	[GPa/(kgm ⁻³)]	0.027	0.027	0.060	0.0005	0.005

Plant fibres have a cellular structure, with a variably sized hollow channel in the centre called the lumen [3]. They are therefore inhomogeneous fibres, which have a large amount of inconsistency compared to synthetically produced fibres. This can cause difficulties with resin impregnation and void content. Published data of natural fibres has a large amount of variation in reported properties [3-5]. Variably may be because of differences in the quality of the natural fibres tested and/or that fibres being tested in different ways. Oskman [6] also suggests that the fibres used for technical applications are the residual fibres from the textile industry, and thus have inferior mechanical properties and fibres lengths.

Oksman [6] compared the static mechanical properties of RTM manufactured made from two different unidirectional flax fibre mats and a unidirectional glass. The unidirectional glass fibre mat had with 90% of the fibres in the main direction. One flax fibre mat was made from mechanically separated fibres. The other (which has the trade name ArcticFlax) had biomechanically retted fibres mat, which is claimed to have superior fibre properties than traditionally retted fibres [7]. Table 2 summarises the results from their work.

Table 2 : Laminate properties from Oksman's testing [6]

Property		Glass	Flax	ArcticFlax
<i>Tensile Strength</i>	[MPa]	817(±35)	132(±4.5)	279(±14)
<i>Young's Modulus</i>	[GPa]	31(±1)	15(±0.6)	39(±6)
<i>Laminate Density</i>	[kgm ⁻³]	1.71	1.23	1.32
<i>Specific Strength</i>	[kNm/kg]	478	107	211
<i>Specific Modulus</i>	[MNm/kg]	18	12	29
<i>Volume-Fraction</i>	[%]	48	32	47

Comparing specific properties the flax-fibre laminate has significantly lower strength and stiffness to the glass-fibre laminate. However, it also has a significantly lower volume-fraction (32%) compared to the other samples tested (~47.5%). The ArcticFlax-fibre laminate had higher specific strength than the mechanically retted flax-fibre laminate as expected, but still significantly lower than the glass-fibre laminate. The ArcticFlax-fibre laminate however, did have the highest specific modulus, 161% higher than the glass-fibre laminate. This shows that the methods used for growing and processing natural

fibres is crucial to their properties, and that flax-fibre laminates have potential in applications the currently use glass fibres.

One of these potential applications is sports equipment. High performance sports equipment is increasingly made from fibre reinforced composites. The high strength to weight ratio of carbon fibre provides significant advantages over traditional materials. However, most handheld equipment has to be 'detuned' as vibrations from impacts transferred to the athlete are uncomfortable and reduce 'feel' [8]. This is usually done by adding materials of lower stiffness, most often glass fibres. Flax fibres have been shown to have damping properties greater than that of glass [9, 10] and have the potential to be used in application in place of glass and/or carbon fibres. Fibre reinforced composites are known to be sensitive to impact damage [11]. Out-of-plane impacts, even at low energies, can significantly decrease the mechanical properties of the material and cause unexpected failure. Sports equipment is subjected to repeated impacts, so the impact properties of any natural fibres being considered for these applications needs to be well understood.

Santulli states in his 2007 literature review focused on the impact properties of glass/plant fibre hybrid laminates that the "a major limitation to the use of these materials [plant fibre reinforced composites] in structural components is unsatisfactory impact performance" [4]. Santulli concludes that development of glass/plant fibre hybrids should focus on manufacturing composites with higher volume -fractions, improved effectiveness of interfaces in dissipating impact damage or improved intermingling of fibres, and a study of fibre configurations in order to maximise impact properties. Santulli also expresses concerns about the control over void content in the laminates and defects, it is suggested further work should use more refined manufacturing methods such as vacuum assisted RTM or injection moulding.

Past literature involving impact on natural fibre laminates has been found to focus on maintaining a fixed thickness between samples when comparing to traditional composite materials, such as glass [12]. Natural fibres, being less dense than glass fibres, present the opportunity to make thicker laminates while keeping the weight of parts the same, providing the ability to increase the out-of-plane properties.

The aim of this work is to produce high volume-fraction (>50%), high quality flax/epoxy laminates and compare their static and dynamic mechanical properties with glass-fibre laminates. To make comparisons between these materials their application needs to be understood. In sporting applications, weight is critical, and specific properties should be compared. As flax fibres have a lower density than glass fibres, flax-fibre laminates of the same areal weight as glass-fibre laminates will have a greater thickness, and increased out-of-plane properties.

2 MANUFACTURING

Flat panels were manufactured using Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). This process was used as it allows for accurate control and repeatability of part thickness. This control is required as thickness is a significant property in impact testing. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the RTM setup used, and Figure 2 shows how the fibre reinforcement was placed in the mould. The mould has internal part dimensions of 300 by 500 mm, and a variable thickness. A peripheral filling technique was used to avoid race-tracking (where race-tracking is defined as the undesired movement of resin through high permeability regions such as the gap between the preform and the mould), which was severe when using a linear fill. Outlet pressure was at atmosphere and inlet pressure at 200 kPa during filling. Once filled, the outlet was clamped and inlet pressure increased to 400 kPa to decrease the volume of any entrapped air.

Figure 1: Schematic of Resin Transfer Mould

Figure 2: Peripheral fill setup in Resin Transfer Mould

Panel thickness was controlled by using 4mm and 6mm spacer plates between the top and bottom surfaces of the mould. Glass and flax fabric with areal weight of 285gsm and 150gsm respectively were chosen. The E-glass was a 2x2 twill sourced from Gurit New Zealand (“Colan AF 303” fabric), and the flax was a 2x2 twill weave sourced from Lineo (“C008 - Ecrú 0001 - loomstate” fabric). Given the material densities (Table 3) this allowed for glass panels of 4 mm thickness, and flax panels of 6 mm thickness to have an approximately equal volume-fraction and areal-weight. It also means panels of the same thickness will have the same number of plies. The panels have balanced and symmetric layups as required for ASTM D7136 impact tests.

Table 4 summaries the panels made. The zero degree orientation corresponds to the long direction of the specimen.

Table 3: Material densities

Material	Density* [kgm ⁻³]
Glass	2580
Flax	1445
Resin	1147

* Glass density supplied by manufacturer, flax and resin density calculated in-house

Table 4: Planned panel properties

Panel	Thickness [mm]	Layup	VF [%]	Panel Areal Weight [kgm ⁻²]
Glass V1	4	[(0/90)(45/45)] _{10s}	55	7.76
Flax V1	4	[(0/90)(45/45)] _{10s}	52	5.22
Flax V2	6	[(0/90)(45/45)] _{16s}	55	7.89

Compaction testing on the E-glass and flax fibres used showed drastically different loads are required to achieve the same volume-fraction (VF) for each layup. To achieve the target volume-fraction of 55% the E-glass required 68.6 kPa of pressure, while the flax required 944 kPa; more than 13 times the pressure. The average properties of the manufactured panels are outlined in Table 5. Limitations with the compaction force available from the RTM mould meant the target thickness was not achieved. Volume-fraction was calculated using a known volume and weight of the laminate, the density of the resin, and the areal-weight of the fabrics. For these calculations it was assumed there were negligible voids in the laminates. Microscopy of the panels confirmed this assumption was valid (Figure 3).

Table 5: Average manufactured panel properties

Panel	Thickness [mm]	Layup	VF [%]	Panel Areal Weight [kgm ⁻²]
Glass V1	3.88	[(0/90)(45/45)] _{10s}	55	7.36
Flax V1	4.17	[(0/90)(45/45)] _{10s}	56	5.58
Flax V2	6.63	[(0/90)(45/45)] _{16s}	56	8.80

Figure 3: Microscopy of flax/epoxy laminate

3 STATIC MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Tensile tests were carried out according to ASTM D3039 [13] with un-tabbed specimens. Figure 4 shows the averages for failure stress and the modulus for each panel configuration. The glass-fibre laminates clearly outperform flax-fibre laminates in both the failure strength and modulus. Average failure stress for the glass-fibre laminate was 361 MPa, while it was 125 MPa for the flax-fibre laminate. A difference in the strength between the length-wise and width-wise samples can be clearly seen, this is due to slightly varied fabric properties in the warp and weft direction as denoted in the

supplier data sheet. The average modulus (measured from 0.1% to 0.3%) for the glass-fibre laminates was 19.95 GPa and 8.15 GPa for the flax-fibre laminates.

Figure 4: Tensile test results; (a) maximum stress, (b) modulus

Samples however, can be compared on their specific properties, which are more relevant in weight critical applications. Figure 5 shows the specific failure stress and the specific modulus for each panel configuration. Again, the glass-fibre laminates outperform the flax-fibre laminates in both aspects. Average specific failure stress for the glass-fibre laminates was 186 kNm/kg, while it was 93.1 kNm/kg for the flax-fibre laminates. The average specific modulus for the glass-fibre laminates was 10 MNm/kg and 6 MNm/kg for the flax panels.

Figure 5: Specific tensile test results; (a) maximum specific tensile stress, (b) specific modulus

Compressive tests were carried out according to ASTM D6641 [14]. Figure 6 shows the results for the compressive failure stress and the specific compressive failure stress. The glass-fibre laminates panels showed superior properties to the flax-fibre laminates with an average compressive failure of 348.5 MPa and 111.9 MPa respectively. Comparing specific properties the glass-fibre laminates had an average specific failure strength of 180 kNm/kg and the flax-fibre laminates 84 kNm/kg.

Figure 6: Compressive results; (a) compressive stress, (b) specific compressive stress

When comparing the properties of the glass-fibre laminates to the flax-fibre laminates, they had a 289% higher tensile failure stress, a 245% higher modulus, and a 311% higher compressive failure load. However, when comparing materials on their specific properties these differences are 200%, 160%, and 214% respectively. Figure 7 highlights the differences in failure modes and surfaces, indicating varying failure mechanisms in each of the composites.

Figure 7: Failure modes and surfaces; (a) flax-fibres laminate in compression, (b) glass-fibre laminate in compression, (c) flax-fibre laminate in tension, (d) flax-fibre laminate in tension

4 DYNAMIC IMPACT BEHAVIOUR

The dynamic impact properties of 4mm glass-fibre laminates were compared to flax-fibre laminates of the same thickness and 6mm flax-fibre laminates of the same areal weight. Tests were carried out in accordance to ASTM D7136 [17] using an Imatek XX instrumented drop weight system. The energy-time history was used to compare energy absorbed through damage mechanisms in the panels. For each impact the peak energy in the panel, the energy absorbed through damage, and the energy returned to the striker (the 'rebound' energy) were noted (Table 6). Visual comparisons of damage patterns were also compared.

Figure 8 shows the energy vs time histories of impacts on the three different configurations tested, 4mm thick glass-fibre laminates, 4mm thick flax-fibre laminates, and 6mm thick flax-fibre laminates. Two impacts were undertaken on the non-perforated specimens. The ~19J impact on the 4mm flax-fibre samples (shown in red) caused penetration. On average, approximately 17J of energy was absorbed before penetration occurred. The glass-fibre samples suffered less damage from impacts than either of the flax-fibre laminates. Table 6 summarises the key impact test energies for each laminate configuration.

Figure 8: Impact testing; energy vs time

Table 6: Average impact energies

Panel – Impact Number	Peak Energy [J]	End Energy [J] (Damage)	Rebound Energy [J]
4mm Glass – 1	18.62	5.37	13.25
4mm Glass – 2	18.70	3.77	14.93
4mm Flax – 1	17.11	---	0
6mm Flax – 1	18.80	10.48	8.32
6mm Flax – 2	19.00	8.22	10.78

Figure 9 shows the force vs displacement for representative samples of each laminate configuration. The 4 mm flax-fibre laminate starts to show severe damage occurring at approximately 2 kN of load, and then puncture occurs at approximately 8 mm displacement. No major damage can be seen in the 4mm glass-fibre samples, and their response is stiffer than that of the 4 mm flax-fibre samples. Severe damage starts to occur at approximately 5 kN for the 6 mm flax-fibre laminate, a 150% increase for a 50% increase in thickness, but penetration does not occur. Initial stiffness is higher than that of the 4 mm glass-fibre laminate. The second impact on the 6 mm flax-fibre laminate shows less damage creation, but a much lower stiffness.

Figure 9: Impact testing; force vs displacement

The 4 mm glass-fibre laminates show only a small amount of local damage around the impact point (Figure 10). In comparison the 4 mm flax-fibre laminates suffered penetration at the same impact energy. Figure 11 (a) shows the top surface of 4 mm flax-fibre sample after an impact, where it can be seen that failure is localised and the impactor punches a circular hole through the top surface. The back surface of these impacts is shown in Figure 11 (b) and a close-up shown in Figure 12. The area of fracture does not extend out towards the edges of the panel significantly. The fracture surfaces are through multiple layers, with no obvious delamination along ply interfaces. This differs from fracture behaviour typically seen in ASTM D7136 tests of glass and carbon reinforced epoxy.

The 6 mm flax-fibre laminates suffered extensive cracking along the backside of the samples as shown in Figure 13 (b). This did not occur in the equal weight 4 mm glass-fibre laminates (Figure 10 (b)). There is little damage visible on the impact surface of the 6 mm flax-fibre samples shows little sign of damage (Figure 13 (a)). The damage between the top and rear surface is not visible due to the specimen's opacity.

Figure 10: Impact samples: 4mm E-glass, (a) impact surface, (b) specimen backside

Figure 11: Impact samples: 4mm flax. (a) impact surface, (b) specimen backside

Figure 12: Impact samples; close-up of 4mm flax backside fracture surface

Figure 13: Impact samples: 6mm flax, (a) impact surface, (b) specimen backside

5 CONCLUSIONS

Flax fibres have been reported as having specific properties equal to, or higher than glass fibres. However, typically flax-fibre laminates are shown to have lower strength and stiffness values compared to glass-fibre laminates. A portion of this has been attributed to low volume-fractions and void content. In this study a custom Resin Transfer Mould was used to create flax-fibre laminates from woven fabric with a volume-fraction of 56%, higher than any other reported volume-fractions to date. Microscopy of the manufactured laminates showed negligible void content. Achieving these laminates required very high compaction forces. The force required to manufacture the flax-fibre laminates at the target volume-fraction of 55% was found to be over 1350% higher than for a glass-fibre laminate of the same volume-fraction.

Quasi-static tensile and compressive testing demonstrated that both the absolute and specific properties of the flax-fibre laminates were lower than that of the glass-fibre laminates. The absolute properties were between 245% and 311% lower, and the specific properties between 160% and 214% lower. These values are for in-plane properties; the lower density of flax-fibres allow for a thicker laminate than a glass-fibre laminate of the same weight. This is expected to be beneficial for out-of-plane properties such as impact performance.

Impact testing on the 4mm thick glass-fibre laminates showed little damage in the samples, with approximately 5 J of energy being absorbed in the first impact. In contrast the impacts on 4mm flax-fibre laminates perforated the samples, absorbing 17.11 J of the ~19 J of energy the impactor had on impact. 6mm thick flax-fibre panels of the same weight as the 4mm glass-fibre panels were also tested. Severe damage in these thicker flax samples started to occur at 5 kN rather than 2 kN as in the 4mm samples, a 150% increase in force for a 50% increase in thickness and weight. The 4 mm flax-fibre laminates had lower impact stiffness than the 4 mm glass-fibre laminates, however due to their greater thickness the weight equivalent 6 mm flax-fibre laminates had higher impact stiffness than the glass-fibre laminates even though the flax laminate's specific tensile modulus is much lower.

Fractures displayed in the flax-fibre laminates in both the quasi-static and impact testing differed from fracture behaviour typically seen in tests on glass and carbon reinforced epoxy. Even at energies close to perforation, the 6 mm flax-fibre laminates showed little evidence of damage visible from the impacted side of the sample, despite large cracking on the back side.

Results indicate that flax-fibre laminates, even on a specific basis, have a lower tensile, compressive and impact performance than thickness or weight equivalent glass-fibre laminates. Potential improvement may be seen by combining glass and flax fibres into a hybrid laminate to leverage the sustainability and lower density of flax fibres.

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